

Research Article

The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All: Promoting Safe Travel Behaviour

Norzaidah Ngali¹*, Norazlina Rahmat², Noorazlin Ramli³, Fatimah Abd Ghani⁴, and Nik Nur Shaadah Nik Dzulkefli⁵

¹ Faculty of Hotel and Tourism Management, UiTM Cawangan Terengganu, Kampus Dungun; norza319@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0002-3975-3873

² Faculty of Hotel and Tourism Management, UiTM Cawangan Terengganu Kampus Dungun; noraz335@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0002-6295-899X

³ Faculty of Hotel and Tourism Management, UiTM Cawangan Terengganu Kampus Dungun; noora115@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0002-6030-4853

⁴ Faculty of Hotel and Tourism Management, UiTM Cawangan Terengganu Kampus Dungun; fatim131@uitm.edu.my; 0000-0003-4078-1043

⁵ School of Electrical Engineering, UiTM Cawangan Terengganu Kampus Dungun; email; niknu5502@uitm.edu.my

Abstract: *The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All is a versatile and innovative travel bag designed to support safe behaviour among travellers, especially during the endemic phase. It encourages travellers to bring and use their ~~own~~ belongings when using public services such as mosques or musolla at ~~the~~ shopping malls or R&R. By providing a reliable means of carrying personal belongings, the Carry All aims to foster confidence and ease in travellers while reinforcing safe practices. The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All is a bag that boasts several unique features catering to the needs of various users. It has a designated compartment for COVID-19 essentials, such as masks and hand sanitizers, and a separate compartment for telekung and sejadah, which caters to Muslim women's needs. Additionally, the bag has interior lighting and a key holder, which makes accessing belongings more convenient, and there is ample space for storing personal items. The bag's versatility makes it practical for travel and daily errands or formal events. Moreover, the lightweight design and cultural significance make it a valuable addition to any wardrobe, suitable for people of all genders. A market survey was conducted using convenience sampling via social media to gather feedback from potential buyers on the Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All. The survey received 117 responses, with 79.5% of respondents indicating interest in purchasing the travel bag. The top-ranked factor for intention to buy the bag was the convenience of having all travel essentials in one bag, selected by 75.2% of respondents. These findings suggest a positive perception and high acceptance of the Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All among potential buyers. The bag was crafted by disabled individuals at PPDK Wakaf TAPAI, Terengganu, using batik fabric to showcase practicality and cultural heritage with a focus on a lightweight design. The collaboration with PPDK Wakaf TAPAI promotes sustainable cultural, social, and economic development in the local community, aligning with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This initiative demonstrates a successful model of community-based sustainable development and positions the Carry All as a travel impulse item.*

Keywords: travel bag, traveller, endemic phase, travel behaviour, safety

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1. INTRODUCTION

The world was stunned by the alarming coronavirus infection (COVID-19) spread. Global travel restrictions and border closures have resulted in significant losses for all sectors, particularly the tourism and hospitality industries. Countries' prolonged travel restrictions and Movement Control Orders (MCOs) have cost the travel and tourism industries an estimated \$5.5 trillion. In addition, the tourism and hospitality industry has lost 100 million jobs (Shaha et al, 2020). The MCO imposed by the

Malaysian government from March 18, 2020, until November 8, 2021, is a measure taken to halt the spread of this infectious disease and level the pandemic case curve throughout the country. Malaysia's tourism and hospitality sector lost approximately RM 3.37 billion in the first two months of the MCO and is anticipated to increase if the cross-country moratorium remains in place for an extended period of time (Dzulkifly, 2020).

In addition to government actions like travel limits or mandatory quarantine (Poonam, 2020), tourists are becoming more worried about their health, which makes it harder for them to travel (Villacé-Molinero et al., 2021). Since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, there has been a shift in people's perceptions of the risks involved (Villacé-Molinero et al., 2021). The concept of perceived risk has gained significant study attention since the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic (Choe & Kim, 2021) because perceived risk plays an essential role in tourists' decisions regarding their travels (Neuburger and Egger, 2020; Zhan et al., 2020).

Furthermore, people would then be motivated to travel more safely in the future. Consequently, The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All has been developed as a significant product that impacts public health and safety by enhancing confidence and ease during post-pandemic travel. This one-of-a-kind Carry All travel kit has a designated compartment for COVID-19 essentials like masks and hand sanitizers and a separate compartment for *telekung* and *sejadah*, which caters to the needs of Muslim women. This bag is specifically designed for female travellers because not all places provide prayer garments, especially when traveling abroad or to remote locations with a small Muslim population. Furthermore, the bag has interior lighting and a key holder, making it easier to access belongings, and plenty of space for storing personal items. The bag's versatility makes it useful for travel, everyday errands, and formal occasions. Furthermore, the lightweight design and cultural significance make it a valuable addition to any wardrobe, suitable for both men and women.

In addition, people with disabilities (PWD's) already face several obstacles in finding gainful employment, and these are compounded by the current epidemic and the increased competition for jobs that it has created (Suhaimi, 2020). Disability rights advocates have been working with other organisations to raise awareness about the social entrepreneurship project since they know the current COVID-19 pandemic disproportionately impacts people with disabilities. Realising that social entrepreneurship will be the best path with great potential for future success for disabled people during this challenging time (Rozali et al., 2018), this innovation project employs people with disabilities to produce the Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All with PPDK Wakaf Tapai.

In conclusion, this innovation project is not only beneficial for social entrepreneurship initiatives among individuals with disabilities but also meaningful to tourists in the post-COVID-19 era. With the information gained from this innovation project, the government's programs and plans, such as the National Entrepreneurship Policy (NEP) 2030, the Malaysian Plan of Action for People with Disabilities (MPAPD) 2016-2022, the 12th Malaysian Plan (RMK12), and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), will be strengthened.

2. METHOD AND MATERIAL

This section focuses on the production process for The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All. The study approach and the outcome of the final development process for the innovative product will be presented in this section.

2.1 Study Approach

As shown in Figure 1, this product innovation project used the Design Thinking Method because it is necessary to empathise with the other person (to gain an empathic understanding of the

problem being solved) and be human-centered (defining the issue as a problem statement). The next stage involves ideation, which involves generating ideas by identifying innovative solutions to the formulated problem statement. After ideation, the next phase is prototyping, where multiple products or specific features within the product are created to explore the solutions generated in the previous stage. Finally, the last step is testing, which involves thoroughly evaluating the complete product using the most effective solutions identified during the prototyping phase.

Figure 1: Process conducted to develop The Breezy Batik Perfect -10 Carry All

2.2 The Breezy Batik Perfect -10 Carry All: Development Process

Empathise Stage

The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All is the newest iteration of the Batik Perfect-10 product line, following the successful development of six previous travel kits. Feedback and recommendations from the previous market survey were gathered and considered in developing this new product. According to the survey findings, a significant number of respondents expressed their preference for specific features to be incorporated into the new concept of the "carry all" product:

1. Each item features its own distinct and personalised design.
2. Convenience in carrying is improved with the inclusion of a strap and a larger size.
3. Despite the conclusion of the pandemic phase, fundamental practices of personal hygiene and safety precautions are upheld.
4. The inclusion of LED lights within the bag makes it easier to locate items.

Define, Ideate, Prototype, and Test Stage

The steps to ensure a seamless development of The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All are outlined as follows (as depicted in Figure 2):

1. *Define*- A collaborative session with the team members to define and generate ideas for product innovation.
2. *Ideate*- A discussion session involving collaboration with PPDK Wakaf TAPAI, the individual responsible for The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All production. Topics covered in the discussion include bag design, colour options, budget considerations, and production schedule.
3. *Prototype*-The process of material and product selection for the exclusive innovation product, which encompasses decisions on fabric choice, label application, and inclusion of products within the kit, was conducted in agreement among all innovators and collaborators. Subsequently, the bag production was initiated by the OKU trainee from PPDK Wakaf TAPAI, marking the final step in the production stage.
4. *Test* - The concluding phase of product development involves testing, wherein a market survey is conducted among potential buyers and users of the innovative product. In this survey, the innovators are keen on understanding the potential buyer's perception, acceptance, and intention to purchase The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All.

Figure 2: Photos related to the Design Thinking Method of The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All boasts four (4) unique and innovative features that make it a versatile and indispensable accessory for modern-day travellers. Firstly, it has a dedicated compartment that enables travellers to store COVID-19 essentials such as disposable masks, hand sanitizers, and rapid antigen tests, thereby ensuring their safety during travel. Secondly, it features a specially designed compartment that allows Muslim women to carry their telekung and sejadah in a single bag, thus promoting convenience and ease of travel. Thirdly, the inclusion of an interior light enhances accessibility and enables travellers to locate their belongings quickly. Lastly, the key holder feature prevents the loss of keys, a common inconvenience many travellers face.

Furthermore, the Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All offers ample storage space for personal items such as wallets, mobile phones, and hygiene kits, making it a comprehensive and versatile accessory. The term "carryall" further reinforces its ability to carry all essential travel items, which is a valuable asset for any traveller. Overall, the Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All is a cutting-edge and adaptable product that effectively meets the needs of contemporary travellers.

Therefore, a market survey on the Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All was conducted through social media using convenience sampling, with 117 respondents providing feedback. The objective was to gather insights into respondents' perceptions and acceptance of the product, particularly after viewing the attached video on the Google Form survey. Respondents were also asked to provide comments or suggestions for improving the Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All. The survey's findings provide valuable feedback that can help enhance the product's features and better meet the needs of potential buyers.

3.1 Demographic Data: Frequency Result of Respondents Profiles

The market survey analysed six items to determine the respondents' behaviour and patterns concerning travel matters. The survey collected data on the respondents' age, gender, location, marital status, educational level, profession, income, and frequency of travel in a year to understand their travel preferences better. Table 1 summarises the demographic profile of the respondents, providing valuable insights into the survey's target audience. These demographic data can be used to tailor marketing strategies and product features to meet potential buyers' needs better.

Table 1: Respondents Profile

Demographic Variables	n	%
Age		
Below 21 years old	37	31.6
21-40 years old	52	44.4
41-50 years old	24	20.5
51-60 years old	2	1.7
Above 60 years old	2	1.7
Gender		
Male	11	9.4
Female	106	90.6
Location of the respondents		
Perlis	0	0
Kedah	1	0.9
Pulau Pinang	0	0
Perak	1	0.9
Kuala Lumpur	9	7.7
Selangor	26	22.2
Putrajaya	0	0
Negeri Sembilan	5	4.3
Melaka	1	0.9
Johor	16	13.7
Pahang	9	7.7
Terengganu	40	34.2
Kelantan	9	7.7
Sabah	0	0
Sarawak	0	0
Marital Status		
Single	65	72.6
Married	29	24.8
Divorce	3	2.6
Educational Level		
PMR	0	0
SPM	4	3.4
Diploma	50	42.7
Degree	40	34.2
Master	23	19.7
PHD	0	0
Profession		
Unemployed	14	12
Housewife	6	5.1

Government Servant	22	18.8
Non-Government	30	25.6
Student	45	38.5
Monthly Income		
Less than RM2500	71	60.7
RM2501-RM4849	18	15.4
RM4850-RM7099	14	12
RM7100-RM10950	12	10.3
More than RM10950	2	1.7
Frequency of Travel in a year		
More than once a month	10	8.5
Once a month	17	14.5
A few times a year	55	47
Rarely	33	28.2
Never	2	1.7

Based on Table 1, most respondents were female, accounting for 90.6% (n=106), while only 9.4% (n=11) were male. The largest age group of the respondents was between 21-40 years old, making up 44.4% (n=52) of the sample, and most respondents were single, accounting for 72.6% (n=65) of the sample. The majority of the respondents had a monthly income of less than RM2500, as most of them were students (38.5%, n=45). Additionally, almost half of the respondents (47%, n=55) travelled a few times a year. These findings provide valuable insights into the demographic characteristics of the sample population.

3.2 Respondents purchase intention towards The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All

The section discusses the respondents purchase intention towards the Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All. The results presented in Figure 3 indicate that many respondents have expressed a favourable intention towards purchasing the Breezy Batik perfect-10 Carry All. Specifically, 79.5% (n=93) of the respondents have indicated a high level of intent, as reflected by their selection of the 4-5 point range on the Likert scale.

Figure 3: Respondents Intention to purchase The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All

Based on the results presented in Figure 4, the most significant factor driving the respondents' intention to purchase the Breezy Batik perfect-10 Carry All was the convenience of having all their travel essentials in one bag, which was selected by 75.2% of the respondents. Additionally, 48.7% of the respondents expressed their intent to purchase the bag to support the disabled individuals who crafted or produced the product. These findings highlight the importance of convenience and social responsibility as key factors influencing the respondents' purchase intentions.

Figure 4: The reason for purchasing The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All

3.3 Respondent Perceptions towards the features of The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All

This section presents the respondents' perceptions of the features of the Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All. The respondents were requested to rank ten items, which included the four unique features of the bag, in order of importance. The four unique features are essential COVID-19 compartment (disposable face mask, hand sanitizer, and rapid antigen test), *telekung* and *sejadah* compartment, interior light, and key holder. The results showed that 35 respondents considered the *telekung* and *sejadah* compartment as the most significant feature of the bag. The hand sanitizer (n=18), COVID-19 antigen test (n=16), multipurpose compartment (n=16), key holder (n=14), disposable face mask (n=10), and travel shampoo and conditioner (n=5) were also ranked highly. However, only one respondent chose antibacterial wipes, travel body wash, and toothbrush and toothpaste as their most important product in the bag. These findings provide valuable insights into the preferences and priorities of the respondents for the compartments and features of the Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All.

In addition, respondents were asked if the interior light embedded in the bag would assist them in finding their belongings. Figure 5 shows that 90.6% of respondents believed that the interior light would be helpful, while 9.4% indicated that it would not.

Figure 5: Perception of Respondents Regarding the Presence of Interior Lighting in the Bag

The respondents provided comments and suggestions for future improvements of the Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All, specifically regarding the sturdiness of the interior lighting. Additionally, the respondents recommended expanding the range of batik designs for better options and selections. Based on the market survey results, the respondents provided positive feedback for the Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All innovation.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, The Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All suggests a favourable perception and widespread acceptability among prospective purchasers. The travel kit can be a lifesaver, particularly when people are wary of travelling at this time. Furthermore, the kit meets the requirements of Muslim women while travelling. In addition, for future products, we plan to improve the quality of the materials used in the Carry All to be more adaptable and durable to withstand any condition. The plan also includes offering different versions or themes for men and women to meet the specific needs of each gender. It was also suggested that the variety of batik patterns be expanded to provide more options and alternatives. As a result, we aim to expand our collaboration with the Tourism Ministry and Kraftangan Malaysia as the driving force behind the empowerment of the batik craft industry through the use of Malaysian batik in society. In addition, this Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All was handcrafted by disabled individuals at PPDK Wakaf TAPAI, Terengganu, using local Terengganu batik fabric to highlight practicality, cultural heritage, and a lightweight design. The partnership between disabled persons from PPDK Wakaf TAPAI promotes the sustainable development of cultural, social, and economic aspects in the local community, in accordance with Sustainable Development Goal 16 (SDGs). This initiative exemplifies a successful paradigm for community-based sustainable development and positions the Breezy Batik Perfect-10 Carry All as a travel impulse item.

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